

Dr. Nabi Bux Baloch Perspective on Education: An Overview ...

Dr. Nabi Bux Baloch Perspective on Education: An Overview (Study Analysis on National System of Education and Education of Teacher)

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Abstract

Dr Nabi Bux (N. A Baloch 1917 - 2011) was one of the remarkable personalities of Pakistan. He was a great thinker, educationist, scholar, researcher and author of various scholarly books. He made splendid contributions to several disciplines that included Islamic studies, Sindhi Civilization and Culture, Education, History, Archeology, Musicology, Anthropology and Folklore. His work exists in Sindhi, Urdu, Arabic, Persian and English language. His service to Sindh stands valuable. He tried to revive the ancient literature as well as folk literature of Sindh. One of his utmost efforts was to explore the ancient manuscripts of Sindhi scholars from the various libraries of the World. He is recognized as the eminent educationist, thinker, and historian of Pakistan; therefore, he was honored with Tamgha-e-Imtiaz (1968), Sitara-e-Quaid-i-Azam (1971), Pride of Performance (1979), President's Award for Pride of Performance (1991), Sitara-e-Imtiaz (2001) Hilal-e-Imtiaz (2011). Dr N.A Baloch was very unique in his views and ideas for educational disciplines. His comprehensive work on education is named: National System of Education and Education of Teacher. In this book, he gave his precious ideas and views to reform our educational system. This brief study sought to understand the Dr N.A Baloch's educational thought and its services to educational process, and discussed this with other aspects of epistemological concepts in terms to respect of its aims, curriculum, and role of teacher in education institutions. As the paper aimed to provide an overview of Dr Baloch's brief biography, his achievements and his profound career.

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Keyword: Dr. N.A. Baloch, Education, Sindh, educational institution, National System, Teacher

1.1. Introduction

Dr N.A Baloch is one of the famous and great personalities of Pakistan. He was a great scholar, educationist, scholar, researcher and author of various books. He got expertise in various disciplines of knowledge. He served as a teacher, professor, administrator and other various posts of several renowned departments. He was also designated as the vice chancellor and Secretary for the Archaeology, Culture, Sports & Tourism, Sindhi Academy, and Sindhi Language Authority. He participated as member of Pakistani Delegation in U.N forums and other important international conferences. Dr. Baloch has devoted much of his life to research on Culture, Islamic studies, Sindhi Civilization, History, Education, Musicology, Anthropology, Archeology, and Folklore. He was well versed in Sindhi Arabic, Persian, English, Urdu, Balochi and Punjabi language. He wrote many precious books and articles. His books and other miscellaneous writings found are in different languages. Dr. N.A Baloch was most qualified and erudite in the field of education; he was affiliated with several distinguished educational institutes. However, he outlined his educational thought in many books, few of them are: 1. Education based on Islamic Values. 2. National System of Education and Education of Teacher. 3. Teacher Education in Muslim Society, 4. The Education Policy 1972, 5. Education in Sindh (Before the British conquest and the educational policies of the British Government), and the various other articles. In these books, he advised the conceptual possibilities for reconstructions of national education system. He also addressed imperative practical shortfalls and gaps in the present educational policies. In fact, his thoughts expound the principles for accruing quality education and could be valuable to improve the performance of students and the teachers. In last, Dr. Baloch was truly concerned towards the field of education and has contributed to improve the national education policies and procedures with zest. Therefore, Dr N.A Baloch honored with Tamgha-e-Imtiaz (1968), Sitara-e-Quaid-i-Azam (1971), Pride of Performance (1979), President's Award for Pride of Performance (1991), Sitara-e-Imtiaz (2001) Hilal-e-Imtiaz (2011).

1.2. Brief Biography of Dr N.A Baloch

Dr Nabi Bux Baloch was born on 16th December 1917 in Village Jaffer Khan Laghari, Taluka Sinjhor, and a small village in the district of Sanghar. He belonged to Laghari family; his father's name was Ali Muhammad Khan.¹ He acquired basic early education from his village, and then got enrolled to primary school at Palio Khan Laghari in 1924.² He moved to Naushero Feroz Madrasah in 1929 for secondary education. He passed his Matriculation in 1936 from Bombay University. He got first class in the matriculation examination.³ And then he got enrolled at Bahauddin Degree College in Junagarh in 1937 and completed B.A (Hons) with first class in 1941.⁴ After this, he took admission in Aligarh Muslim University in 1943 and completed his masters in Arabic. He got scholarship from the British Government of India for further higher studies at the Columbia University in New York. He did Master's and Ph.D. degrees during 1946-1949. His doctorate topic was "A National system of education for new state of Pakistan".⁵

Dr. N.A Baloch chose to pursue his education from the greatest and renowned scholars in their respective disciplines, few of them are: Allama Abdul Aziz Memoni, Dr Hadi Hussain, Dr

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Syed Zafar al Hasan, Prof. Muhammad Habib, and Prof. Rasheed Ahmed Siddiqui.⁶

No doubt, Dr Baloch`s professional career was distinguished, after completing his Ph.D. Dr. N. A Baloch joined the U.N internship program, he got opportunity to become permanent part of U.N. but he refused and returned to homeland to serve his own country.⁷ Early, Dr. N.A Baloch started job at the Ministry of Information and Broadcasting (Pakistan) then, he went to Damascus as Public Relations Officer for Pakistan Mission. He returned to homeland for Sindh University. He was offered job as professor at University of Sindh, he got this opportunity, and he founded the first ever Department of Education in 1951 in country.⁸ Dr. N.A Baloch served as Vice Chancellor of the University of Sindh from 1973 to 1976. He initiated various departments including the Centre for Pakistan Studies and Pharmacy department in University of Sindh. He helped to establish the various campus of University of Sindh. Shah Abdul Latif Campus and Allama I.I. Kazi campus was established in his period, Central Library of University and Sindhology department were strengthened in his profound era. He arranged the generous grant for University and facilitated several opportunities for scholarships.⁹

The Federal Government of Pakistan got his services in 1976. Firstly, Dr. N.A Baloch was appointed as Secretary (O.S.D) of Ministry of Education. He was also designated as Chairman of National Institute of Historical and Cultural Research, where he launched many publications and miscellaneous writings.¹⁰ Dr. N.A Baloch was also appointed the first Vice Chancellor of the Islamic international University at Islamabad in 1980. He established many department of university within a very short time.¹¹ Dr. N.A Baloch was also appointed as advisor of the National Hijra Council in 1983, there he organized various programs and publications regarding the celebration of the 15th century of the Islamic era. He returned to Sindh in 1990. Dr. N.A Baloch was assigned as Chairman of the Sindhi Language Authority from 1990 to 1994. Many ancient books were translated and edited and published behalf of his personal efforts.¹²

1.3. Introduction to his widespread works:

As it is known that Dr. N.A Baloch spent his life in learning, teaching and compiling the books, he wrote approximately more than 100 numerous books covering a variety of subjects like Education, Culture, literature and History of Sindh. He read Islamic perspective and western perspective regarding education. He credited to contribute a number of works in education filed to his which includes: 1. National System of Education and Education of Teacher. 2. Teacher Education in Muslim Society. 3. Hasil al Nahj: (The Initial work on Education and curriculum in the Sub-continent in Persian language, authored by: Makhdoom Ja`ffar Bubakani. Dr. Baloch discovered and edited this books and wrote chapter wise summary in English in 1969), Institute of Education, Sindh University. 4. Education Based on Islamic Values, imperatives and Implications. 5. Education in Sindh: (Before the British conquest and the Educational policies of the British Government), Sindh University Press in 1971. 6. The Education Policy 1972, (Implications and implementations). 7. Curriculum And Teacher Education: (The volume on Muslim Education was presented in 1st World Education Conference at Makkah in 1977, it was Edited by N.A. Baloch jointly with M.H. Al-Affendi, published by: Hodder and Stoughton, King Abdul Aziz University, Jeddah, 1980). He was also founder of Journal of education (University of Sindh) and many other well-known journals.

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1.4. Dr Nabi Bux Baloch`s views on Education:

Islam highly emphasized the education and its pursuit, Education was essentially a community concern in the Muslim society. Islam enlighten that it is education which brings human being closer to Allah and also enhances respect in society. According to Dr. N.A Baloch, in Muslim society, education received the greatest possible attention from the very beginning. The education is compulsory for every individual member of the Muslim society, man and women. Originated in the injunction of the Holy Quran and the teaching of the Prophet (May Peace of God be on Him). Iqra (Read) was the very first word of Quran and as such the Prophet lay it down that acquisition of knowledge is obligatory upon every Muslim, man and women. He selected a team of teachers and sent them to the various sections of the new Muslim community throughout Arabia. His direction to the teachers: make it easy, do not complicate.¹³

In addition, he stated: Islam emphasizes that a society cannot be developed unless its human resources are properly utilized through cultivation of knowledge. The Holy Prophet declared education the foremost duty of every Muslim man and woman.¹⁴

Dr. N.A Baloch advised that the education system of Pakistan should be based on Islamic ideology and own Muslim cultural and educational heritage, Dr. Baloch`s viewed that: The education system in Pakistan should be inspired by Islamic ideology emphasizing among many of its characteristics those of universal brotherhood, tolerance, and justice.¹⁵ He argued, a new educational re-organization in Pakistan must harmonize the best from the past with the present for the future progress of the country.¹⁶ In further, he also proposed: A sound understanding of our own educational heritage must provide the foundational base in which to build up a new educational structure incorporating the best that the modern western or eastern system of education offers.¹⁷ He further wrote: The ideals of education cannot be borrowed; these must be rooted in the socio-cultural foundation of the society.¹⁸

Dr. N.A Baloch was well aware that education cannot be acquired by policies and rules but some other requirements are essential, therefore, Dr. Baloch wrote: Education is a positive force for social change, but it can become effective only when the masses consciously participate in educational developmental activities at their own level. In a developing country like Pakistan, where a vast majority of the people is illiterate, development in educational and social domains often poses a serious problem. The masses feel that formal schooling is not related to their immediate economic needs, does not fulfill their social-cultural requirements, and alienates them from cultural traditions.¹⁹

No doubt, the progress of a country depends on the education, education plays vigorous role for development as well as sovereignty of country, Dr. N.A Baloch shares the views of Quaid e Azam Muhammad Ali Jinnah, the founder of Pakistan, in his message to the Pakistan educational conference (November 1947) He said: there is no doubt that the future of our state will and must greatly depend upon the type of education we give to our children, and the way in which we bring them up as future citizens of Pakistan.²⁰ Dr. N.A Baloch also wrote: education and enlighten opinion are also two only safe guards against any external aggression. National education is the only sure and permanent guarantee of national strength, in the present of conflict and confusion, no country can be ignorant and be free and strong at the same time.²¹

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Dr. N.A Baloch gave the preference that objective of education is that development of every person of society. He stated, According to our social philosophy individual and community (or society) is complementary to each other. Therefore, the aims and objectives of our national education must be directly related to the development of the individual as a member of the society.²²

1.5. Building the Teacher's professional skills Competences:

Teachers are a crucial part of educational institutions. They regarded as an essential element for the progress of country. Therefore, teacher must be well proficient, trained and skillful. According to Dr. N.A Baloch, the nation needs teachers who are superbly fitted to their important task. It needs teachers who respect personality, who are community minded, who act reasonably, and who know how to work cooperatively with others. It needs teachers whose native gifts have been highly developed through sound general and professional education. It needs teacher who understand how children grow and develop, who know how to guide learning and mediate knowledge effectively.²³

Dr. N.A Baloch also said that the basic concept that the teachers must be prepared as nation builders with adequate professional competence to fulfil the needs of national education indicates that the education of the teacher must necessarily vary in different systems of different societies. Even in the same society, teacher education must necessarily be related to the varying school system of the various parts of the country.²⁴

In addition, Dr. N.A Baloch also recommended some qualities for teachers; these qualities were elaborated from official reports of the commission on teacher education of the American council on education.

General Qualities

- Respect for personality
- Community mindedness
- Reaction behavior
- Skill in cooperation

Towards professional Qualities

- Increasing knowledge
- Skill in mediating knowledge
- Friendliness with children
- Understanding the children
- Social understanding and behavior
- Good citizenship in the school as society
- Skill in evaluation.²⁵

Dr. N.A Baloch considers that teacher is an integral part of educational system; they understand the educational problems of institutions. According to him, it is essential to realize that only the teachers with personal viewpoint on education can solve our educational problems. Moreover, such a personal viewpoint functionally related to the achievement of educational objectives is the only effective way of integrating the preparation of the teachers with their education tasks or the theory with their practice.²⁶

Dr. N.A Baloch believes that teacher training enhance professionalism and produce quality

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teacher, therefore, he wrote: the education of teachers in Pakistan should equip the prospective teachers with basic skills, understandings, and knowledge necessary to enable them as teacher to bring about the change which is essential for the achievement of educational objectives.²⁷

He also discussed the role of administration, he counseled, these immediate next steps for bringing about the essential changes are need simultaneously in the administrative system, in the programs of instruction in the schools and in the programs of teacher education. The quality of education in the schools cannot be ameliorated without improving the quality of both, the teacher's training and the school administration. Similarly, the education of teachers will largely depend upon the improvements made in the administrative policies and producer.²⁸

He believes that no scheme, plans or proposals as such, can solve the educational problems. They only show the direction of educational change and improvement. The actual enforcement of any plan or proposals must necessarily depend upon the will and determination of the nation as a whole, the legislative action of the central and provincial governments, the administrative leadership of the Department of Education, and the influence and alertness of the teaching profession.²⁹

Dr. N.A Baloch recommended that these following essential changes are needed:

- Reorganization of the education departments
- Professional preparation of the administrators
- Differentiating the school curriculum
- Freedom in designing curriculum
- Having organized platform of teacher education
- Increasing the professional rewards
- Raising the level of education and the status of primary teacher
- Freedom of the design the curriculum
- Abolition of the external examination
- Extending the period of training.³⁰

1.6. Conclusion

Dr. Nabi Bux Baloch was a versatile genius and man of many capabilities. He was basically a real teacher with all the qualities of an educationist, a reformer, who knew so well about the Islamic, western's educational system and past as well as the present of the educational system. Dr N.A Baloch has expounded his ideas of education on the basis of his personal experience. He gave many valuable suggestions and remedial measures for improvement of National education system, and gave the broad roadmap for our institution and teachers. He also highlighted imperative practical shortfalls and visible wide gaps in our educational system. He believes that it will be suicidal for us if educational modernization continues to be adjourned in favor of any other motives of national development and defence. The present article discusses the various aspects of Dr. N.A Baloch's educational thoughts and its applications to educational system. It also describes the role of teachers and has also explained the reconstruction of the education system and its operational success must depend upon the teaching and administrative competences.

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